

STUDIES ON THE PRECIPITATION OF THORIUM HYDROXIDE.
PART II*. INTERACTION OF THORIUM CHLORIDE AND
POTASSIUM HYDROXIDE

BY RAMESHWAR PRASAD AND ARUN K. DEY

A quantitative study of the association of potassium and chlorine ions with the precipitated material by the interaction of thorium chloride and potassium hydroxide solutions has been made. The precipitation of thorium hydroxide is complete with 3.6 equivalents of alkali when the concentration of thorium salt solution is 0.0625M, and 3.8 equivalents when the concentration is 0.0156M. In both the cases complete precipitation occurs in acidic medium. It has also been noted that the association of potassium ions has been found to increase, in general, with increase in the quantity of alkali added while that of chlorine diminishes under the same conditions. With increase in temperature and with higher dilution, the association of both ions diminishes.

It has been observed by the workers from these laboratories (vide Ghosh, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, Part II, *Chem. Sec.*, 1958) that the amount of alkali required for complete precipitation of a heavy metal hydroxide from its salt solution is always less than the theoretical amount. There is also an association of the corresponding anions with the precipitate which led Britton (*Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, London, 1943, 40, 44) to postulate the formation of basic salts in such precipitation phenomena.

Dey and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 181; 1950, 27, 66; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1948, 17A, 93) do not agree to the view of the formation of basic salts. They regard the presence of anion in the precipitate purely due to the adsorptive forces and that the adsorption of the anion results in the generation of free alkali, which in its turn completes the precipitation of the hydroxide. We have observed (*Vig. Pari. Anu. Patrika*, 1960, 3, 155) that from a 0.0625M thorium chloride solution 3.6 equivalents of alkali are able to precipitate thorium completely from the solution.

In this communication observations have been recorded on the changes in the medium and the adsorption of ions, when thorium hydroxide is precipitated from its salt solution with potassium hydroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

A solution of thorium chloride (BDH-LR) was prepared, and thorium and chloride ions were estimated by the usual methods; the ratio of these ions was 1 : 4. A solution of potassium hydroxide was prepared from a BDH-AnalaR sample and it was standardised against acid using methyl red as an indicator. All other chemicals used were of the reagent grade.

Procedure.—In several 100 c.c. volumetric flasks 20 c.c. portions of standard thorium chloride solution were taken; varying amounts of KOH solution were added and the volumes raised to 100 c.c. in every case. The precipitates were allowed to settle overnight and the supernatant liquids were quantitatively analysed for H^+ or OH^- and Cl^- and K^+ ions.

* Part I : *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1959, 28A, 350.

For the estimation of acidity or alkalinity, an aliquot portion was titrated against a standard alkali or acid using methyl red as indicator. Chloride ion was estimated by titration against a standard silver nitrate solution using dichlorofluorescein as an adsorption indicator.

For the estimation of potassium ions, 10 c.c. of the supernatant liquid was diluted to 100 c.c. and the concentration of potassium determined with the help of a flame photometer (B. Lange, Model 5).

The experiments were performed at three different temperatures. The individual solutions and a bottle of water (used later for dilution) were kept in a thermostat maintained at a constant temperature (within $\pm 0.1^\circ$). The solutions were mixed and kept in the thermostat for 24 hours.

All concentrations in the following tables and figures are the final ones and are expressed in mg. *M* per litre.

TABLE I

H⁺ -ion concentration in the supernatant liquid.

Conc. of $\text{Th}^{4+} = 50$ mg. ions. Conc. of $\text{Cl}^- = 200$ mg. ions.

Ratio $\text{Th}^{4+} : \text{OH}^-$	Hydrogen ions (in mg. ions).		
	20°.	50°.	70°.
1:3.0	16.8	17.7	12.6
1:3.2	8.5	15.5	9.5
1:3.4	4.7	8.0	6.0
1:3.6	2.7	1.5	2.1

TABLE II

OH⁻ -conc. in the supernatant liquid.

Conc. of Th^{4+} and Cl^- same as in Table I.

Ratio $\text{Th}^{4+} : \text{OH}^-$	Hydroxyl ions (in mg. ions).		
	20°.	50°.	70°.
1:3.8	0.2	0.6	0.8
1:4.0	0.5	1.0	1.1
1:4.2	7.3	8.5	9.1
1:4.4	18.0	19.7	19.7
1:4.6	29.0	31.2	32.2
1:4.8	39.0	42.0	42.3
1:5.0	51.0	51.2	55.0

The medium became just alkaline when 3.8 equivalents of the alkali were added, though thorium had already been precipitated completely at 3.6 equivalents.

It may be noted that thorium is precipitated in this case with 3.8 equivalents of alkali and the supernatant liquid is just alkaline when four equivalents of alkali are added to the system.

In order to economise space, the adsorption of potassium and chloride ions are represented graphically in Figs. 1 and 2, the observations being omitted.

TABLE III

*H⁺ -ion conc. in the supernatant liquid.*Conc. of Th⁴⁺ = 12.5 mg. ions. Conc. of Cl⁻ = 50 mg. ions.

Ratio Th ⁴⁺ : OH ⁻ .	Hydrogen ions (in mg. ions).		
	20°.	50°.	70°.
1:3.0	4.6	5.0	5.0
1:3.2	3.6	2.9	2.8
1:3.4	0.8	0.8	0.8
1:3.6	0.4	0.3	0.2
1:3.8	0.1	0.1	0.1

TABLE IV

*OH⁻ -ion conc. in the supernatant liquid.*Conc. of Th⁴⁺ and Cl⁻ same as in Table III.

Ratio Th ⁴⁺ : OH ⁻ .	Hydrogen ions. (in mg ions).		
	20°.	50°.	70°.
1:4.0	0.3	0.4	0.5
1:4.2	2.2	2.3	2.4
1:4.4	5.2	5.2	5.2
1:4.6	7.6	8.3	8.8
1:4.8	10.6	11.0	11.5
1:5.0	13.3	14.1	14.5

DISCUSSION

From the results it is noted that precipitation is complete while the alkali added is still in deficient quantity. The value approaches four equivalents when the precipitants used are dilute (Tables I—IV).

We observe that the association of potassium ions with the precipitate goes on increasing with increasing amounts of alkali to a point beyond four equivalents and then finally decreases (Figs. 1 and 2). At higher temperatures, however, the association has a tendency to decrease, probably

due to the decrease in the surface activity of the hydroxide. At the lower concentration the precipitation values approach the theoretical equivalent.

The association of chloride ions with the precipitate decreases with increasing quantity of alkali added. The first few points in Fig. 2 (curve E) do not agree to this because precipitation

FIG. 1

Adsorption of K^+ and Cl^- by the hydroxide, precipitated from $0.0625M$ thorium chloride (final conc.), by varying amounts of potassium hydroxide.

Solid lines represent the association of K^+ and broken lines that of Cl^- .

Curves: A 20° , B 50° and C 70° .

Curves: D 20° , E 50° and F 70° .

FIG. 2

Adsorption of K^+ and Cl^- by the hydroxide, precipitated from 0.0156 *M* thorium chloride (final conc.), by varying amounts of potassium hydroxide.

Solid lines represent the association of K^+ and broken lines that of Cl^- .

Curves: A 20°, B 50° and C 70°.

Curves: D 20°, E 50° and F 70°.

remains incomplete with the small amount of alkali added. The association of chloride ions, in general, diminishes with rise in temperature.

These observations are in accordance with a hypothesis advanced earlier from these laboratories (Dey and Ghosh, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong., Part III, Chem. Sec., 1951*) on the behaviour of

hydroxides. According to the scheme, thorium hydroxide is precipitated by the interaction of thorium and hydroxyl ions. The hydroxide behaves as shown by the following equations:

Equation (i) shows the basic character of the hydroxide; this would explain the greater association of Cl^- ions in a medium, which is not alkaline. With increase in alkalinity the basic character would diminish and thus the association of chlorine with the precipitate would also diminish. Equation (ii) shows the liberation of a proton from the positively charged material Th(OH)_3^+ . This liberation would be less improbable from Th(OH)_4 , which is neutral. This is responsible for the acidic properties of the hydroxide, and thus the association of K^+ ions would be favoured as the concentration of alkali is increased. This is also evident from our experimental results.

In a predominantly alkaline medium, equation (ii) will be favoured, but at the same time would lead to the formation of an inert product, ThO_2 , by the mutual interaction of the acidic and basic properties of the hydroxide, as shown by equation (iii), resulting in the liberation of water. Thus in the presence of an excess of alkali, the adsorptive capacity will diminish due to the growing inertness of the medium.

The authors express their gratitude to Prof. S. Ghosh and to the late Dr. S. P. Mitra for their interest in the work. They also thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for supporting the work and for the grant of an assistantship to one of them (R.P.).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

Received May 19, 1960.